

is popular, but it has short, bold, red grains, and consumers prefer fine-grained, white rice. We tested IR50, with fine white grains, at Tirur.

TKM9, ADT36, PY2, and IET4786

were sown with IR50 on 5 May and transplanted on 6 Jun at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Fifty kg NPK/ha was applied basally before transplanting and 50 kg N/ha was applied in 2 equal splits 15

and 30 d after transplanting.

IR50 yielded less than TKM9 (see table), but it was resistant to mealybug and stem borer. It is becoming popular in sornavari. □

Influence of Zn on distribution and mobility of ⁵⁹Fe in two rice cultivars

C. P. Ghonsikar, D. C. Phulari, D. K. Jadhav, and G. U. Malewar, *Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science Department, Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani 431 402, India*

We evaluated the effect of Zn on distribution and mobility of ⁵⁹Fe on 2 rice cultivars grown on a calcareous Vertisol with pH 8.2, 49.7% clay, 0.62% organic carbon, 0.65 ppm DTPA Zn, 0.5 M NaHCO₃, P₂O₅, 18.5 kg EDTA/ha, and 4.5 ppm Fe.

Two 6-wk-old seedlings of Tuljapur and Jaya were washed with demineralized water and placed in glass bottles with 250 ml of 1/2 strength Hoagland nutrient solution. Zn was added to 5, 10, or 15 µg Zn/ml. 5 µCi/plant of ⁵⁹FeCl₃ in HCl was derived by root absorption, injection into the second internode of plant stems, or smeared on leaf blades. Plants were removed from the bottles on day 6, washed with distilled water, rinsed with 0.1 N HCl, and washed again with distilled water. Roots, stems, and leaves were separated and analyzed. Dried plant samples were digested with a triacid mixture and radioassayed.

Plant parts treated with ⁵⁹Fe retained maximum ⁵⁹Fe within them,

Table 1. Effect of Zn application on distribution or translocation of ⁵⁹Fe in various plant parts of rice cultivars, Parbhani, India.

Application	Zn (kg/ha)	Distribution/translocation of ⁵⁹ Fe (% total activity in rice plant)		
		Root	Stem	Leaf
<i>Tuljapur</i>				
Root	5	56.2	39.5	4.3
	10	49.1	45.2	5.7
	15	52.8	41.1	6.2
Stem	5	41.9	49.5	8.6
	10	46.7	50.4	2.9
	15	37.6	55.3	7.1
Leaf	5	5.4	43.2	51.5
	10	4.0	42.7	53.5
	15	5.9	34.9	59.2
<i>Jaya</i>				
Root	5	58.9	34.5	6.6
	10	53.7	41.2	4.7
	15	53.7	40.4	5.9
Stem	5	43.7	48.3	8.0
	10	46.7	49.6	3.7
	15	38.4	54.8	6.8
Leaf	5	5.7	43.1	51.2
	10	4.6	41.5	53.9
	15	6.4	35.2	58.4

and 41 to 51% was translocated to other plant parts (Table 1). A considerably higher proportion of leaf-smeared than stem-injected ⁵⁹Fe was retained in leaves of both the cultivars. Zn application levels had no consistent effect on ⁵⁹Fe translocations.

Mobility ratios (Table 2) showed that ⁵⁹Fe mobility was greatest in the

Table 2. Effect of Zn application on mobility ratio of ⁵⁹Fe in various parts of rice cultivars, Parbhani, India.

Application	Zn (kg/ha)	Mobility ratio (%)		
		Root	Stem	Leaf
<i>Tuljapur</i>				
Root	5	—	0.7	0.1
	10	—	0.9	0.1
	15	—	0.8	0.1
Stem	5	0.8	—	0.2
	10	0.9	—	0.1
	15	0.7	—	0.1
Leaf	5	0.1	0.8	—
	10	0.1	0.8	—
	15	0.1	0.6	—
<i>Jaya</i>				
Root	5	—	0.6	0.1
	10	—	0.8	0.1
	15	—	0.8	0.1
Stem	5	0.9	—	0.2
	10	0.9	—	0.1
	15	0.7	—	0.1
Leaf	5	0.1	0.8	—
	10	0.1	0.8	—
	15	0.1	0.6	—

stems of rice plants. The stem functioned as a sink for Fe, independent of application method. The two cultivars did not have markedly different Fe translocation patterns.

Studies on ⁵⁹Fe translocation indicate that foliar application of Fe gave better retention in functional or active parts (leaves and stems), and that it may protect against nutrient-induced Fe chlorosis. □

Audiovisual rice production modules

A 43-module series of audiovisual lessons in rice production may be purchased from IRRI. The modules cover seven topic areas: production management; growth and morphology of rice; production problems and techniques; weeds, diseases, and their control; pests and their control; research design and analysis; and soil relationships. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Department, Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.